

FORMATIVE AND SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

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Annotation: Assessment is a very important part of any educational program, it helps in evaluating the concepts learned by students in the classroom. Teachers should use such assessment methods and techniques that allow them to evaluate not only the subject, but also the meta-subject results of students at various stages of the educational process.

Key words: *formative assessment, summative assessment, meta-subject skills, evaluation*

The assessment should be carried out both for the purpose of final fixation of student achievements, and for the purpose of formation and development of subject and meta-subject skills and abilities. That is, the teacher, who has always remained the controller, should share the assessment tools with the student, reveal to him the grounds or criteria by which the assessment is carried out, and give him the opportunity to use the assessment results to his advantage. Assessment is a very important part of any educational program, it helps in evaluating the concepts learned by students in the classroom. Assessment is a tool that teachers cannot work without, since periodic assessment of students' abilities helps teachers to summarize their teaching methods. Evaluation is also used in the corporate sector to check the effectiveness of training programs, as well as to see how well employees perceive the program through their feedback. There are two main assessment systems, called formative and final assessment. There are many differences between the two assessment systems, which will be discussed in this article. First, let's talk about formative assessment. Formative assessment is a method aimed at confirming learning goals or objectives, as well as improving learning standards. This is achieved by identifying and then eliminating problems in the educational process. Formative assessment allows the teacher to monitor the student's learning as he receives feedback that he can use to improve his teaching methods. This method allows students to better understand their strengths and weaknesses in order to work on target areas that need to be improved. This method is good for teachers, as they can identify problem areas and help students experiencing difficulties overcome them. Teachers receive high-quality feedback from students using the formative assessment methodology. This allows them to learn material that should not be

taught or used to evaluate students. Formative assessment is a continuous process that is often referred to as an internal assessment method. This allows the teacher to evaluate the value of the training program. What is the final grade? Summative assessment is a cumulative assessment method, as it is performed at the end of a semester or any other academic unit to see how well the student has received from the training. It is so called because it summarizes the student's learning at the end of the curriculum. The summative assessment focuses on the result, so it is called the external evaluation method. It is used to check whether students have achieved the objectives of the curriculum. Teachers receive the help of a benchmark to assess the achievements of students.

We can discuss the differences between the formative and final assessment as follows:

- formative assessment is qualitative, and the summative one is quantitative;
- formative assessment is a continuous process, while summative assessment is an event that occurs at the end of the training unit;
- summative assessment is formal and takes the form of quizzes and written tests, while the formative assessment is informal, such as homework and projects;
- the purpose of the formative assessment is to improve what has been learned, while the purpose of the summative assessment is to prove the amount of learning that has taken place;
- formative assessment is aimed at determining the individual achievements of each student and does not involve either comparing the results demonstrated by different students or administrative conclusions based on the results of training;
- formative assessment is understood as assessment during training, when the knowledge, skills, values, as well as communicative skills of the student are analyzed, feedback is established about the student's successes and shortcomings. The main purpose of such an assessment is to motivate the student for further education, planning goals and ways to achieve them.

The pedagogical technology of formative assessment assumes a certain algorithm of interaction between teachers and students in the organization of the educational process and consists of nine stages. The purpose of the first stage of the technology is to plan the educational results of students by topic. The specifics of this pedagogical technology presupposes the implementation of this stage at the stage of development of the teacher's work program. The teacher's work program should plan and distribute or group the educational results (subject, meta-subject, personal) of students on educational topics. At the second stage, it

is necessary to plan the educational results of students' activities. When formulating educational goals, it is necessary to take into account their properties such as unambiguity, accessibility for students to understand. At the third stage of the technology implementation, it is necessary to formulate the tasks of the lesson as steps of student activity, in other words, to define the tasks of the lesson reflecting the specific actions of students in the lesson. The solution of all the tasks of the lesson should lead to the achievement of the goal.

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